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MEETING PARTNERS ONLINE

Among people currently in relationships, we identify those who met their partner through online dating, based on data from the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) collected between 2020 and 2025.

DATA ON NEARLY 50 000 RESPONDENTS AGED 18-49

Across 12 countries, the share of people who met their current partner online ranges from 6.8% in Croatia to 21.9% in Finland, showing notable regional differences. In most of the studied countries, the percentage falls between 12% and 18%.

Looking at relationship duration, the share of those who met online is highest among people whose relationships' duration at the time of the survey was at most five years (from 13.7% in Croatia to 36.9% in Finland), and gradually decreased the longer the relationship spanned— 9.6% to 22.3% for 6–10 years, and 2.9% to 11.1% for over 10 years.

This pattern shows that newer relationships (those that began within the past five or ten years) are much more likely to have started online, compared to older relationships, reflecting the growing role of digital platforms in partner formation and marked differences between countries.

PERCENTAGE OF PEOPLE WHO MET THEIR CURRENT PARTNER ONLINE BY RELATIONSHIP LENGTH

GGs PROVIDES VALUABLE INSIGHTS INTO PARTNERSHIP FORMATION AND DYNAMICS.

Source: Generations and Gender Survey Round II – wave 1 (data from 2020-2025)

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